

CHALLENGES IN TEACHING VETERINARY TERMINOLOGY IN ENGLISH

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Abstract. *This article explores the challenges associated with teaching English veterinary terminology to non-native veterinary students. It highlights the complexities arising from the specialized nature of veterinary terminology, cultural differences in language comprehension, and the need for effective pedagogical strategies. Additionally, it discusses the significance of incorporating interactive learning activities, visual aids, and contextualized examples to facilitate effective comprehension and retention of veterinary terminology. Underscores the importance of ongoing assessment and feedback mechanisms to tailor instruction to the diverse linguistic needs of learners, ultimately promoting proficiency in English veterinary terminology.*

Keywords: *veterinary, terminology, grammatical rules, word, foreign language, English, term, student, teacher.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqola ingliz tilidagi veterinariya terminologiyasini ona tili bo'lmagan talabalarga o'rgatish bilan bog'liq muammolarni o'rganadi. Bundan tashqari, veterinariya terminologiyasini samarali tushunish va esda saqlashni osonlashtirish uchun interfaol o'quv faoliyati, ko'rgazmali qurollar va kontekstli misollarni o'z ichiga olib, muhokama qilindi. Natijada, talabalarning turli lingvistik ehtiyojlariga ko'ra o'qitishni moslashtirish uchun baholash va qayta aloqa mexanizmlarining muhimligini ta'kidandi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *veterinariya, terminologiya, Grammatik qoidalar, so'z, for, ingliz tili Ingliz, termin, talaba, o'qituvchi.*

English veterinary terminology is the basis of acquiring professional foreign language communicative competence. It allows the corresponding specialist to perform his functions effectively and to learn and exchange critical information with foreign colleagues. Veterinary terminology, like any terminology, is subject to the laws and norms of the respective language. Veterinary terms are used and applied according to lexical and grammatical rules. Students' knowledge of terms and their correct grammatical use justifies the expediency of studying the meaning of terms, the methods of their creation, and the rules of grammatical combination. Therefore, an important aspect is the creation of new didactic and teaching-methodical materials. They will contribute to the student's acquisition of new knowledge regarding the correct use of professional terminology in compliance with word formation norms, avoiding errors in speech, and creating new terms.

Therefore, we believe that the process of learning foreign veterinary terms is an essential aspect of the process of training a future specialist in the relevant field. The difficulty of learning foreign terms usually lies in the fact that English language veterinary terminology differs from Ukrainian in terms of grammatical categories (gender, plural, case, etc.), word formation, phonetic rules, and rules of usage and spelling. However, the terminology is also similar since many veterinary terms are of Latin or Greek origin. In the case of the Ukrainian language, borrowed from English, and therefore, having learned them in the relevant specialized subjects, it is usually easier for a student to repeat them in professional foreign language classes. Thus, we focus on International scientific conference 334 synchronous training of specialized veterinary subjects with a professional foreign language. Foreign veterinary terms are acquired mainly by memorizing terms and their translation. This statement is also supported by A. Abduelo et al.: "Students often

learn terminology by memorizing and recalling it, which belongs to the category of passive learning and is recognized by students as an inefficient pastime that students often avoid." Such training, according to scientists, is often accompanied by students' misunderstanding of the meaning of such terms [1, p. 3].

To learn English-language veterinary terminology, a student must have basic knowledge of the English language. Here it is worth noting that the mandatory external examination in English mostly leveled the level of students' knowledge and facilitated the educational process for teachers in higher education institutions. It should be mentioned that before the compulsory external examination in English, there were frequent cases when there were persons in the group of veterinary students whose knowledge of the English language was both at a very high level and at a low level. Therefore, the teacher wasted a lot of time explaining to such students the basic grammar rules and vocabulary that the student should have mastered at school. When studying English veterinary terminology, student mainly faces many problems. One of the most important is the grammatical category of singular/plural veterinary terms of Latin or Greek origin.

The set of veterinary terms in the English language is formed using general grammatical rules, that is, by adding the ending -s, -es, -ies to the word, for example, a cow – cows, a pig – pigs, a cell – cells. Some veterinary terms have the wrong form: a sheep – sheep, an ox – oxen, fish – fish, a goose – geese. There are also collective nouns that mean only the plural: cattle, swine, or only the singular: anatomy, alcohol. While studying the grammatical category of singular/plural nouns does not pose significant problems, as they mostly fall under the general grammatical rules of the English language. However, the opposite case applies to veterinary terms of Greek and Latin origin. To form their plural/singular form, knowledge and competence in the Latin language is required, for example, alveolus (singular) – alveoli (plural), bacillus (singular) – bacilli (plural), bacterium (singular – bacteria (plural). Another main problem in studying English veterinary vocabulary by Ukrainian students is the grammatical category of gender. In the Ukrainian language, the gender category is entirely developed thanks to the endings of nouns, verbs, adjectives, etc. In English, this category is not so well developed. Concerning English veterinary terminology, it should be noted that the genus category will not be reflected by endings but by the formation of Riga, the Republic of Latvia November 3–4, 2022 335 entirely new words. As we can see, the genus category in English veterinary terminology refers mainly to the names of animals and is formed by forming an entirely new designation, not by endings. However, there are veterinary terms in Ukrainian with a clearly defined genus category, but not in English. Another critical aspect of learning English veterinary terminology is syntax, namely the coordination of parts of speech. Terms belonging to different parts of the language are coordinated with the help of endings in both Ukrainian and English languages.

To correctly match English veterinary terms, the student needs to know a list of word-forming suffixes that can be used for conversion. For example, anatomy – anatomical, to inject – injection, pain – painful – painless. In the Ukrainian language, the declension of words when agreeing on parts of speech always occurs, depending on gender, number, case, time, etc. In English, it is rare, for example, domestic animals, or domestic animals, a domestic animal, a domestic animal, etc., will be translated into English as domestic cattle, where the word domestic is an adjective. Concerning learning the correct pronunciation, it is worth noting that students often have problems pronouncing the letter combination th-, for example, thermometry, catheter, and arthralgia. Often problems occur with pronunciation in terms with the letter combination -ch-, which will be pronounced in Ukrainian as [к], for example, bronchi, chemical, cholesterol,

chronic; the letter combination –eu– will be pronounced as [ю], pasteurization, pleuritic; letter combination –ph– – [ф], for example, esophagus, lymph. It is worth noting that the correct pronunciation of English veterinary terms also depends on the language of origin of the terms [5, p. 311].

English-language veterinary terminology is the main component of professional foreign-language communicative competence. Knowledge and correct usage of the acquired knowledge of veterinary terminology in a foreign language removes most of the language barriers that arise during foreign language communication of veterinary specialists. The main difficulties that a foreign language teacher faces when teaching students English veterinary terms are determined by the specifics of their origin, categories of singular/plural, word formation, mutual agreement of terms, gender. In our opinion, the solution to most problems lies in systematic work – to a lesser extent with a teacher, to a greater extent – independently.

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